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Contributi Proposti

Title: Hydrothermal deposits associated with volcano-tectonic structures, south of Aureum Chaos (Mars)

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Abstract: Volcano-tectonic structures are widespread in Mars' chaotic terrains. Those structures include collapsed lava conduits, radial and concentric fractures, y-shaped junctions, fissure vents associated to lava flows, and pit chains. Between the southern edge of Aureum Chaos and the northeastern edge of Arsinoes Chaos, we observed a mineralogical variation in a small light-toned deposit in proximity of volcano-tectonic structures. The appearance of this light-toned deposit is different from the light-toned deposits hosted inside the nearby chaotic terrains, that appear instead layered, sulfate-bearing and that are located in closed basins, suggesting a possible lacustrine/evaporitic depositional environment. In this case the deposit is not located in a basin, does not show internal layering nor the presence of sulfates. The extent of the deposit is limited at ~ 1.3 km, but other patches are visible in the area, suggesting that perhaps the hydrothermal deposits have been exhumed locally but are still buried for most of their extent. CRISM data were analysed using the summary products for a first identification of hydrated minerals. The band depth at $1.9 \mu\text{m}$ has significant values in correspondence of the light-toned deposit, suggesting occurrence of hydrated minerals (Viviano-Beck et al., 2014). The spectral analysis allowed a clear distinction between the basaltic bedrock hosting pyroxenes and the light-toned deposit where Fe-Mg phyllosilicates were identified. In particular, the absorption at $2.28 \mu\text{m}$ was interpreted as belonging to smectite, since the other Fe-Mg phyllosilicates have absorptions shifted at $2.3 \mu\text{m}$ having more Fe than Mg (Clark et al., 1990). The occurrence of smectite and the location of the deposit nearby a system of deep fractures and collapsed lava conduits suggest that the light-toned deposit could represent the result of hydrothermal deposition and alteration of the basaltic bedrock (Inoue, 1995). The complex web of grabens, fissures and fractures could have been a preferential path for circulating hot fluids at the late volcanic stage of the area. The whole region surrounding Valles Marineris was already considered by Schulze-Makuch et al. (2016) as a possible hydrothermal target on Mars, given the magmatic-driven tectonism affecting the area and the occurrence of hydrated minerals. We propose this relatively small deposit as a hydrothermal target.

Thematic section: Pianeti e satelliti